

POLICE MISCONDUCT AND PUBLIC TRUST: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF DISTRICT BAGH, AZAD KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between police misconduct and public trust in District Bagh, Azad Kashmir. The primary objectives are to identify the types and prevalence of misconduct by police officers as perceived by local citizens; to examine how such perceptions influence trust in law enforcement; and to explore the demographic and socio economic factors that mediate this relationship. Using a mixed methods design, the research combines quantitative data from a structured survey of 500 residents across urban and rural areas with qualitative insights from 20 in depth interviews with community leaders, victims, and police personnel. The findings reveal that the most commonly reported police misconduct includes bribery, excessive use of force, abuse of authority, and neglect of duty. Higher incidences of perceived misconduct correlate strongly with lower levels of public trust, especially among younger and lower income citizens. Qualitative data underline that transparency, accountability, and accessible complaint mechanisms are critical in restoring confidence. The study concludes that to improve public trust, systemic reforms are needed: better training in human rights and professional ethics; stricter oversight and disciplinary procedures; and community engagement initiatives to bridge the perception gap. The policy implications extend to the regional administration as well as civil society stakeholders, suggesting a framework for reform that could be adapted in similar contexts.

Keywords: Relationship, police misconduct, public trust, District Bagh, Azad Kashmir, police officers, local citizens, law enforcement, socio economic factors.

INTRODUCTION

Police department is one of the major agencies provided with the responsibility of maintaining conformity and social order in the society. Maintenance of trust between public and police is one of the key areas of research in contemporary crime and criminal justice system as this leads to better situation of law and order in society. Number of factors is associated with public trust in police including the professionalism of police officers. Police misconduct is a key component of distrust among public and police. Procedural, criminal

and civil rights misconduct of police are among the important parameters leading towards the public procedural and outcome based distrust in police.

It is a crystal clear fact that people will not approach police for tackling the public disorder situations if they do not trust police. In such kind of scenario, the peace of society surely moves comparatively on a vulnerable stage. A lot of efforts have been made (Suddle, 2003) to document nature and style of policing but rare efforts have been made to explore the public police distrust as barrier for police to perform

their duties in a professional way. There is a need to study the factors that are causes of police's misconduct in AJK Police.

In 21st century, police is considered as important and significant part of criminal justice system of any country. Police is a personification of the state nominated personnel to put in practice the enforced law, protect property and maintain social order in civilian matters. The term is most commonly associated with police services of a state that are authorized to exercise the police power of that state within a defined legal or territorial area of responsibility. Police forces are often defined as organizations separate from any military forces or other organizations involved in the defense of the state against foreign aggressors (Police Study Institute, 2009). Schaefer (2000) defines police as a branch of government which is charged with the preservation of public order and tranquility, the promotion of public health, safety and morals, and the prevention, detection and punishment of crimes.

With respect to policing, police misconduct has emerged out as a great cause of concern for authorities. Police misconduct is a violation of human rights. There is a need to contextualize issues that constitute police conduct. Police misconduct refers to the violation of state and federal laws or the violation of individuals' constitutional rights by police officers. Police misconduct describes to the improper actions taken by police officers on official duties or miscarriage of justice and discrimination. Police misconduct comprises deliberately attaining wrong confessions, false arrest, creation and the use of fake evidence, including false witness, false imprisonment, bullying, police brutality, police corruption, political interference, surveillance abuse and police drug etc. Packman (2009) defines police misconduct as any action performed by a law enforcement officer that is unethical, against established employment guidelines, unconstitutional, or criminal in nature. He further explained that police misconduct in abuse of police authority. Sometime police misconduct used interchangeably, this term refers to a wide range of procedural, criminal and civil violations. Figure no 1 explore the types of police misconduct. Tuch and Weitzer (2004) explain

that there are four types of police misconduct in procedural process that is verbal abuse, excessive force, unwarranted Stops and corruption. Procedural misconduct started when a person went to the police station to report the case against someone, this is the start of the legal process. As per law and ethics, officers should provide the person comfortable environment before starting the procedure, for instance; say welcome, secure, ensure for justice, follow up the case honestly,. Instead of all these, the normal situation of police shows that they start their work according to the socioeconomic status and societal position of the complainer.

There are many departmental policies and guidelines are written specifically to address potential breaches of constitutional protections or legal guidelines, but in some may they do not meet the given criteria. Civil rights in every society have a fundamental status which cannot be breached by anyone. There are numerous example i.e. officers' behavior with women, children and old age people. Sexual harassment cases are often victims of such civil misconduct (Mallon, and Tranger 2016). Furthermore, criminal misconduct is the use of police resources for personal use, security breaches, & profane language (O'Connor, 2005). Crime is defined as the violation of written rules and regulation set by the state. In every public department there is a defined statute that all those persons, whom are attached to a particular organization, should be followed. The Police department is also one of the public serving departments it has a constitution that needs to be in practice while police are on duty. Excessive use of force is usually seen in civil and procedural processes. Criminal misconduct includes assault, battery, theft and false arrest, etc. In police agencies where officer rank misconduct as very serious, the officers are more willing to report peers for misconduct. There was very little difference between the officer's individual attitude toward the misconduct and what they believed their peers' attitudes would be toward the conduct (Klockars et al., 2004)

Management is part of this culture. Because of this horizontal and vertical loyalty, misconduct can continue for a prolonged time and is difficult to tackle (Crank, 1998; Skolnick, 2002). Rothwell and Baldwin (2007), however,

argue that this may be exaggerated and that police culture not only contains elements that foster a code of silence, but also elements that may promote whistle-blowing. Their survey even indicates that police officers are slightly more likely to blow the whistle than civilian public employees. Whether the complainant is a citizen or a police officer, an allegation of misconduct can be handled through several procedures which have different goals and the burden of proof (Dixon, 1999, p. 60; Ede and Barnes, 2002). such as The police is invested with far reaching powers and a significant degree of discretion in order to perform their duty: to uphold the law and protect citizens. Much of their work is enacted immediately and can only be scrutinized afterwards. Because of these aspects of police work, it is crucial that the public can place their trust in the police and that they can hold the police accountable for their actions. Accountability is especially important when police actions may be labeled as misconduct (Harrison and Cunneen, 2000). A history of police scandals in many Western democracies, and a strong criticism of how the police conduct their internal investigations have resulted in much debate on how they should be held accountable (Harrison and Cunneen, 2000). A key issue is the advancement of external control over the police: “who polices the police” (Ede and Barnes, 2002). The complaints process can, at one extreme, be fully organized and controlled by the police or at the other extreme be fully organized and controlled by an independent and external organization. External control can take place by independent review of the quality of the internal investigation by boards consisting (partly) of citizens “civilian oversight” or by boards that have the authority to investigate complaints “civilian control” (Walker, 2001)

Public Trust in Police

Public trust in the police develops because of the result of their desires. Furthermore, the public is end client of police administrations so they plan to get police support and protection in different circumstances, particularly where they trust their security is at hazard. Along these lines, their level of trust indicates their confidence in the ability of the police to

guarantee their protection in the given circumstances (Hurst et al., 2000). So also, if nationals perceive the police to be very strong to manage crime then they would trust the police. The previously mentioned idea dated as the instrumental approach. Instrumental approach coordinates to the trust in any establishment that emerges from the subjects' observations which have made in connection with the effectiveness and the preparation of the foundation. Police procure a lot of power to regulate shared behavior.

The Relationship between Police Misconduct and Public Trust

It is widely observed that the police in any given society has a difficult job to fulfill. Dealing with criminals and facing the harm on a day to day basis is indeed an excellent calling. Although seen as difficult, there is an underlying sentiment in the general public that the job of law enforcement officers is relatively straightforward. The role of police in modern society is often a conflicted one. The public seems alternately torn between crying out because of abuses of police power and calling for increased police protection from the ills of the world. The police, as a social institution, seem to be caught between these two extremes, trying to balance liberty with security. Out of this inherent tension is the place of the police in modern society, many of the positive and negative aspects and roles of the institution begin to emerge.

Today, the relationship between police and the public has become so alarming in our country. A citizen and a policeman both have negative attitudes and behavior. The attitude of policemen towards their profession is very careless. People commonly prefer to solve their problems by themselves, instead of taking help from police or other law and enforcement agencies. This trend needs to be changed. There is a need that policemen have to bring a change in their professional attitude towards the public dealing. This change will help to improve the all over law and order situation of AJK and Pakistan. There must be the cooperation level between both the policemen and citizens equally so that both can perform their duties

and also bear their responsibilities for a good society and the country.

In 2002, during the military government, various steps were taken to bring reforms in policing. The colonial Police Act 1861 was substituted by Police order 2002 with an objective to make the police a positively professional, service adaptive, operationally autonomous, democratically culpable organization yet many reforms are needed in Police department in order to have effective policing in Pakistan (Javaid & Ramzan, 2013).

Azad Jammu & Kashmir Police

The AJK Police is a public servant and the implements of the law whether civil or criminal. It is tragic that the very arm of the government that expected to implement the law is breaking it. At the point when AJK Police indicate carelessness, ineffective and wastefulness in keeping up peace and order, it gets to be distinctly perilous for a normal national to walk openly in the society. This behavior is additionally delivered impediments to powerful policing and undermines professionalism. Even with constantly expanding demonstrations of lawlessness, social disorder, arranged theft, political deaths, police is included in gathering of backhanders and private blessings. This circumstance delineates the police to negative image and negative authorizes particularly in Punjab, where police image is an open scandal of debasement. This examination will investigate the information on police misconduct or violent behavior and deterrents to compelling policing to streamline factors making wastefulness and ineffectiveness to policing in the AJK.

Global scenario on police misconduct and public trust

Since the late 1950s, the need for an effective system for dealing with complaints against the police has been a “live issue” in the UK (Maguire 1991: 177). Police misconduct thus presents a particular threat to the rights and liberties of individual citizens. Moreover, it can also undermine the credibility of the criminal justice system, the effectiveness of policing, and the legitimacy of government (Bayley 1995: 93). Research that has been conducted has noted

that the motive in suing the police is not chiefly financial, “but to bring facts to light, or to bring the police to book” (Ward 2002: 21). Given that the chances of success in the civil courts in actions for damages are “dramatically higher” than pursuing a remedy through the complaints or criminal process (Ward 2002: 21), it is not surprising that many complainants do not bother with the formal complaints system, but turn instead to civil action (Smith 2004: 23; Reid 2002: 194). Litigation is proving a more effective way of achieving vindication for victims of police misconduct than complaints procedures. Moreover, civil actions can attract publicity and thus stimulate debate about police misconduct (Harrison and Cragg 1995: 9). A complaints process for police misconduct must therefore command the confidence of the public, in order to achieve public support for the police (Goldsmith and Lewis 2000; Smith 2001). On the other hand, a negative experience with the police complaints system can have a wider negative effect on confidence in the whole police organization since public perception of the effectiveness of the complaints system is an important component of the process of accountability (Strudwick 2003:36). Prenzler and Ronken (2001), in their theoretical paper on the best form of control of police conduct, identify three models for police complaints systems: internal, civilian control and civilian review.

Accountability is especially important when police actions may be labeled as misconduct (Harrison and Cunneen 2000: 6). On a broader level the police force can be held accountable for its Policies regarding police misconduct. For instance through an analysis of official information on complaints of misconduct and how their dealt with. However, official data is often discarded because it would only show ‘the tip of the iceberg’ and leaves an unknown ‘dark number’. Klockars even stated: “official data on corruption is best regarded as a measure of police agency anti-corruption activity than the actual level of corruption” (Klockars, et al. 1997:4).

A history of police scandals in many Western democracies and a strong criticism of how the police conduct their internal investigations have resulted in much debate on how they should be

held accountable (see Harrison and Cunneen 2000: 2). A hot item is the advancement of external control over the police: 'who polices the police' (Prenzler en Ronken 2001; Walker 2001; Ede en Barnes 2002). Most Western democracies have installed systems, such as an Ombudsman, where there is at least some independent control or oversight. Examples are The Police Complaints Authority (the UK), the Special Investigations Unit (Ontario, Canada) and the Police Integrity Commission (New South Wales Police Service, Australia). The differences between internal and external investigations are not the only relevant aspect of investigations into police misconduct.

The Police Integrity Commission (New South Wales, Australia) makes a distinction between two types of complaints. Category 1 complaints are the most serious and include allegations such as perverting the course of justice, soliciting or accepting bribes and involvement in the cultivation and/or supply of prohibited drugs (PIC 2003: iv). Or in other words: behavior that constitutes corruption and other serious criminality; matters warranting dismissal from the Police Service; and matters in which it is unlikely that there will be public confidence in an internal police investigation. Category 2 complaints are all other complaints (PIC 2003: 3).

The Queensland Police Service (Australia) also makes a distinction between two types of complaints: Misconduct (including official misconduct), which is more serious, is defined as conduct that: (a) is disgraceful, improper or unbecoming an officer; or (b) shows unfitness to be or continue as an officer; or (c) does not meet the standard of conduct reasonably expected by the community of a police officer. Breach of discipline matters typically involve incivility, rudeness, intimidation, inappropriate behaviour, inaction or failing to comply with procedures (Ede and Barnes 2002: p115-116).

Objectives of the Study

The present study will be conducted keeping in view of following objectives:

- To study the socio-economic status of victims in Bagh AJK
- To analyze the level of procedural based trust among the complainants on AJK Police

- To explore the nature of relationship between police misconduct and public trust
- To investigate procedural, civil and criminal misconduct among the police officers of the AJ&K police

Limitation of the study

- The data will only be collected from the year of 2016
- The cases of terrorism will be excluded from the study
- The cases from Murder will not be studied
- Cases resolved through Community Based Dispute Resolution will not be targeted
- Juvenile delinquency cases will not be considered in this study
- **Statistical Hypotheses**
 - There are differences in procedural, criminal and civil rights police misconduct on the bases of socio-economic status of the complainants
 - There is a negative relationship between procedural police misconduct and police procedural distrust of the complainants

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Confidence in the police has always been investigated as one of the broader social queries in police-public relation. In 2000, Paolineet al., conducted several studies to inspect officers' attitude toward citizen support and trust. They had examined various factors such as the determinants of officers' perception of citizens. These factors have been classified into two groups: individual and occupational variables. In connection to individual variables, inspection shows that gender and educational attainment were significantly associated with officers' attitude towards citizens' support and trust (Jackson& Bradford, 2009).

Organizational factors (such as fairness) and personality traits have been shown to be related to employee behavior. Perception of fairness is one of the strongest organizational factors related to performance (Colquitt et al., 2005; Cropanzanoet al., 2007), particularly counterproductive work behaviors (Rotundo&Sackett, 2002). The personality trait, "negative affect" has been shown to be not only a strong predictor of counterproductive

work behaviors (CWB), but also a moderator between perceptions of fairness and many employee behaviors and attitudes (Dalalet al., 2012; Penney & Spector, 2005). This is one reason why some researchers have suggested combining both approaches (Colquitt et al., 2013).

Pakistan inherited an over eighty years of age police framework from the British at the season of independence (Suddle, 2001). The fundamental system of Pakistan's Police constrain has been taken from the Indian Police Act 1861. The police are guilty for different services, for example, ruining wrongdoing, distinguishing and arresting criminals, executing orders and warrants, and collecting and announcing data with respect to open peace and order. After partition, there was a need to change it as per the prerequisites of the new period (Wynbrandt, 2008).

As per Punch's (2000) order of police misconduct, demonstrated In above, can be gathered as takes after: kickbacks, shake downs, protection of illegal activities, and the settle are forms of "conventional" corruption and the rest are forms of misconduct (corruption of expert) or of crime (opportunistic burglary, coordinate criminal activities, and chipping or paddling). Sociological discussion of "subculture" gives another clarification to excessive utilization of force. Promoters of this point of view (Skolnick, 1966; Stark, 1972; Westley, 1970) propose that there are sure norms, values and administrative desires that furnish officers with basis to enjoy such activities. Prenzleretal (2013) thinks of a procedure to control police violence. Researchers recommend that guaranteeing police responsibility and teach in the force can help in lessening or controlling police violence. Harris and Worden (2012) examined police disciplinary systems in regard to the effect of sanctions' severity on future incidents of police misconduct, measured by likelihood and timing of citizen complaints on officers with previous complaints during their career at a northeastern, large police department. The findings from this longitudinal cohort study show that officers who received more severe punishments were more likely to obtain a complaint in the future compared to officers who received lesser sanctions for a similar type

of complaint (Harris & Worden, 2012). Robert (2010) procured standard of police mentality to human relations is unbiased attitude. Most cops are promised to the standard of absence of prejudice, as well as they inflexibly accept that they are truth be told reasonable and fair-minded in their dealings with persons of distinctive racial, ethnic, or religious gatherings. Initiate and in-administration preparing schools for police declare equity, fairness, and absence of bias. Yet, as the Law Enforcement Coordinator of California has watched, cops "regularly neglect to understand that their preferences make fair-mindedness inconceivable. Accepting, as numerous do, that 'Negroes have criminal propensities prompts oblivious segregation'".

The philosophical basis of policing in a democratic society rests on the notion of policing by consent where the public puts its trust and confidence in police officers to serve and treat people, even the offending ones in the community, with the respect and dignity human beings deserve as their birthright (Alderson, 1979). Policing has at its paradigm the notion of service to the community in which it operates, even if at times force may be a legally allowed option to take to carry out such service. The main objectives of policing worldwide are those of protecting society against threats and detecting, stopping, and pursuing crime (Presthus, 2009). The prevalence of police deviance is a much-debated statistic, and Porter and Warrander (2009) argue that its determination is "rife with problems" because of varying practices among police complaints commissions. While some researchers suggest that corruption is endemic to police culture across the globe, others argue that incidents are rare (Hunter, 1999). Despite such statistical problems, incidents of police deviance do surface from time to time all over the world. Some examples in the UK involve suppression of evidence, beating of suspects, tampering with confidential evidence, and perjury (Dean, Bell, & Launch's, 2010).

UNODC (2006) describes seven typical categories of police misconduct: physical abuse, prisoner mistreatment, evidence manipulation, corruption, unauthorized disclosure of information, extortion, and sexual misconduct.

However, as Johnson (2005) argues, appropriate use of force can, in many cases, be very difficult to discern, especially because the line that separates brave from brutal is not always visible in a policing situation. In the police world, the bravest are sometimes the most brutal and they tend to be the ones most admired and protected by other police officers. Police officers used their positions to extract money and gifts (Johnson, 2005).

Police organizations collect, hold, or have access to a significant amount of information, some of it of a private nature about victims, witnesses, crimes, and suspects, and much of it confidential. That same information has a market value for criminals, journalists, and private investigators that can be realized by unscrupulous police staff with access to it (UNODC, 2006). Information about operations or investigations can also be sold. Where police activities or investigations are targeting a particular person or location, that information can be invaluable not only to any criminal involved, but also to journalists who may be looking for an interesting scoop (UNODC, 2006).

Police crime is a well-known problem in such places as Mexico (Davis, 2007) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (Maljevic et al., 2008), but it does not occur only in those countries. It is found in the UK (Porter and Warrender, 2009), United States (Klockars et al., 2006), Australia (OPI, 2008), and Norway (as this study shows) as well—although on a smaller scale. Police crime tends to be discovered when investigating police complaints. Police crime is here defined as an international crime committed by police officers on duty. Policing police crime is defined as enforcing the law on potential and actual criminal employees in the police organization (Seneviratne, 2004). Dean et al. (2010) developed a matrix of seriousness for police misconduct and crime that we apply in this research. The concept of police governance deals with several normative principles, including accountability, transparency, participation, responsiveness, equity, and the rule of law. The concept is based on an assumption that police organizations need to benchmark operations against governance standards (Jones, 2009).

Smith (2009) argues that a regulatory network has become a part of the police governance framework under the guise of performance management and extended its reach into accountability Mechanisms. Lack of public trust and confidence in accountability mechanisms has made regulation a more attractive means for ensuring the delivery of fair and effective policing services.

Theoretical Framework of the Research **Human Relations Theory**

Prior to a move to a closer understanding of the dimensions of organizational structure, it is important to examine the research interested in the behavior of people in organizations. Human Relations theories, begun around the 1940's, addressed the basic assumptions about the relationship between organizations and people. According to Argyris (1970), those organizations that see through the lens of the Human Relations perspective focus on people, groups, and relations among them. Because the Human Relations perspective places a high value on humans as individuals, things typically are done in a very open and honest environment, providing employees with maximum amounts of accurate information so they can make informed decisions with free-will about the future.

Human Relations theory draws on a body of research and theory built around the following assumptions: 1) organizations exist to serve human needs, 2) organizations and people need each other, 3) when the fit between individuals and the organization is poor, one or both will suffer, and 4) a good fit between individuals and the organization benefits both with human beings finding meaningful and satisfying work, and organizations getting the human energy and talent they need (Bolman and Deal 1991).

Furthermore, researcher will try to explore the same ideas in Pakistani context and examine the public relations with police in wide spectra. It will help us to understand the situation between the lines. This theory is corner stones of individual and organization environment with public. The ideas share above will help the researcher in the proposed dissertation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The researcher used two types of tools for collecting data for their research from the target population i.e. qualitative and quantitative methods. In this current research study the quantitative research method was used to access the target stakeholders and get initial data for this research study. As the quantitative study method is to cover a large population and a long process, but the importance of this current study stress to follow the quantitative method for this current research study.

Quantitative Research is a formal, systematic process in which numerical data are used to obtain information about the world (Burns & Grove, 2005). Quantitative research makes use of questionnaire, surveys and experiments to gather data is revised and tabulated in numbers, which allows the data to be characterized by the use of statistical analysis (Hittleman and Simon, 1997).

Research method

There are many more methods available for a quantitative research. The Tools and Instruments use in quantitative research playing a pivotal role in every research. These tools and instruments are the backbones of research studies. The research method is a strategy of inquiry, which moves from the underlying assumptions to research design, and data collection (Myres, 2009)

Data collection

The researcher uses for the collection of data during the research process is known as the method or tool of data collection. The tool is a questionnaire through.

Research Instrument

Tools & instruments are the weapons of every researcher accessing the needed data. Without these research weapons a researcher remains helpless and nothing. The tools of filling out the questionnaires, surveying, focus group discussions, interviews, public forums etc are the main instruments and weapons for a researcher and the researcher have rights to select one or many as according to the demand of their study.

In this research study the only tool and instrument that were used as the closed ended questionnaires as an instrument and research weapons for the target community.

According to (Parahoo, 1997), a research instrument is “a tool used to collect data. An instrument is a tool design to measure knowledge attitude and skill.” According to (Leary, 1995), there are distinct advantages in using a questionnaire vs. an

Interview methodology: questionnaires are less expensive and easier to administer than personal interviews; they lend themselves to group administration; and, they allow confidentiality to be assured. (Robson, 1993) indicates that mailed surveys are extremely efficient at providing information in a relatively brief time period at low cost to the researcher.

Universe

As the every research study, assuming and we assumed and define here that the area where the research study is conducting is the study of the universe. The universe is the set of individual or objective having common observable characteristics (Iftikhar, 2014). The study will be conducted in the District Bagh, AJK represent a rich socioeconomic. The population of the study will be the complainants who visited the police station in District Bagh Azad Jammu & Kashmir.

Sampling Method

There are two types of sampling method.

- Probability or random
- Non-Probability or Nonrandom

The researcher used in this study Purposive sampling“ A purposive sample is a non-probability sample that is selected based on the characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Sample size

A sample is a subgroup of the target population that the researcher plans to study for the purpose of making generalizing about the target population. Current research study’s sample size is 40. Sample size depends upon factors such as the time and money available to collect data (Hair, 2006). They also depends on the statistical analysis used in the study (Saunders,

Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). According to Hair (2006), small or very large samples have a negative impact on the statistical test because either the sample is big either not big enough to make generalizations or too big to reach any conclusions.

3.4 Pre -Testing

Before finalization it is so useful to make a pre-test of the instrument using in every research study. Because we didn't know what will be the community response in action on the research questions. It not only provides the way to modify the question, but also explore a new understanding of the research problem. Prior to finalization 10 questionnaires were pretested. After the construction of the questionnaire, it was pre-tested to check the work ability of measuring instrument. The questionnaire was finalized on the basis of the feedback received from the pre-testing. Ten respondents were selected randomly for pre-testing. After pre-testing the tool, three more questions were added and response categories were modified according to the willingness of the respondent. Layout and order of the questionnaires were also modified.

A pretest refers to a trial administration of an instrument to identify flaws. When a questionnaire is used as a data gathering instrument, it is necessary to determine whether the questions and directions are clear to the subjects and whether they understand what is required from them. This is referred to as a pre-testing of a questionnaire. (Polit & Hungler, 1995).

3.5 Coding

Coding referred to an analytical process in which data, in both quantitative form (such as questionnaire result) and qualitative form (such as interview transcript) are categories to facilitate analysis. A code is a rule for converting a piece of information (e.g. A letter, word, phrase, or gesture) into another form or representation (one sign into another sign), not necessarily of a some type. Through coding researcher transform the data into a form understandable by computer software. This minimizes the chance of errors from coding and increases the reliability of data. Through

coding, the answers of respondents were converted into numbers. Coding is an analytical process in which data is categorized to facilitate analysis. Coding means the transformation of data into a form understandable by computer software. The classification of information is an important step in preparation of data for computer processing with the software. One code should apply to only one category and categories should be comprehensive (Iain Hay, 2005). According to Earl Babbie "Coddling is a process of raw data either manifest or latent content into standardized, Quantitative form" (Babbie, 1992).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis is often used to explore the data and helps to examine the distribution of values for a particular attribute. It converts numbers into meaningful conclusions in accordance with the purpose of study. In order to analyze present research the researcher followed the principles of quantitative research. There are two methods of statistical analysis, i.e. Univariate analysis and Bivariate analysis.

Univariate analysis

Univariate analysis is the straightforward form of quantitative analysis. The analysis is carried out with the description of a single variable in term of the appropriate unit of analysis. It looks at a range of values, as well as the central tendency of the values. It describes the pattern of response towards the variable. It describes each variable on its own. Variables one at a time is called Univariate analysis. This is the usual starting point in analyzing survey data (Bohrnstedt, 1991).

Percentage

The sample frequency table will be made to describe the basic characteristics of the respondents. In order to bring the data into comparable form, percentage of various categories of the data will be worked out in the present study. The percentage will be calculated by following formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where F= frequency and N=total number

Mean

Mean is the most familiar average. It is defined as a value obtained by dividing the sum of all observations by their number. The mean may correspond to either a population or a sample of the population (Chaudhry& Kamal, 1968)

The mean= sum of all values of data/number of values in the data

$$\bar{X} = \sum X/n$$

Median

The median is defined as a value which divides a data set that have been ordered into two equal parts, one part comprising of observations greater than and the other part smaller than it. Or more precisely, the median is a value at or below which 50% of the ordered data lie (Chaudhry& Kamal, 1968).

$$\text{Median} = 1 + h/f (n/2 - c)$$

Bi-Variate Analysis

Bi-variate analysis is one of the simplest forms of quantitative analysis. It involves the analysis of two variables in order to see if the variables are related or not, for instance independent variable and dependent variable. Bi-variate analysis can be helpful in testing hypothesis of association and causality.

Chi-square

Chi-square is the simplest and most useful statistical method for the social sciences researchers. It is also an effective test for

studying the existence of the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable of hypothesis. In the current research chi-square was applied to verify the relationship between the two variables dependent and independent.

$$X^2 = \sum (O-E)^2/E$$

Ethical considerations

McNamara, (1994) identifies five ethical concerns to be considered when conducting survey research. These guidelines deal with voluntary participation, no harm to respondents, anonymity and confidentiality, identifying purpose and sponsor, and analysis and reporting. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the study. Burns and Grove (1994), define informed consent as the prospective subject's agreement to participate voluntarily in a study, which is reached after the assimilation of essential information about the study.

The subjects were informed of their rights to voluntarily consent or decline to participate, and to withdraw participation at any time without penalty. Scientific honesty is regarded as a very important ethical responsibility when conducting research. Dishonest conduct includes manipulation of design and methods, and retention or manipulation of data (Brink, 1996).

Table 4.1 What type of police miss conduct you often face

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Procedure	22	55.0
	Civil	13	32.5
	Criminal	5	12.5
	Total	40	100.0

what type of police mis conduct he often face

Interpretation:

Table 1.1 and Figure 1.1 show that out of 40 respondents, 55% are of the procedural police miss conduct people often face, 32% civil and 12% criminal police miss conduct people face.

Table 4.2 what type of police wing mis conduct he faced

Interpretation:

Table 1.2 and Figure 1.2 sows, that out of 40 respondents, 42.5% are of the view that in police misconducting includes traffic police and 32.5% Narcotic police and 25% city police.

Table 4.3 Do you think police misconduct is an issue in city

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Yes	29	72.5
Valid No	7	17.5
Valid Any other	4	10.0
Total	40	100.0

do he think police mis conduct is an issue in city

what type of police mis conduct he often face

Interpretation:

Table 1.3 and Figure 1.3 show that out of 40 respondent, 72.5% are of the view that police miss conduct is an issue in cite, 17.5% are of the view that police miss conduct is no issue in city.

Table 4.4 Does police miss conduct make him feel less comfortable in his own neighborhood

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	14	35.0
	No	11	27.5
	any other	15	37.5
	Total	40	100.0

does police mis conduct make he feel less comfortable in his own neighborhood

Interpretation:

Table 1.4 and Figure 1.4 show that out of 40 respondents, 35% are of the view that they feel less comfortable due to police misconduct in neighborhood and 27.5% are of the view that they are not feel less comfortable due to police misconduct.

Table 4.5 Have you ever had a personal experience with police

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	yes	8	20.0
	no	32	80.0
	Total	40	100.0

Interpretation:

Table 1.5 and Figure 1.5 show that out of 40 respondents, 20% are of the view that there is personal experience with police end 80% are of the view that there is no personal experience with police.

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Traffic	17	42.5
	Narcotic	13	32.5
	City police	10	25.0
	Total	40	100.0

Table 4.6 who do he think is more effected by police miss conduct

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	poor	28	70.0
	rich	12	30.0
	Total	40	100.0

Who does he think is more affected by police miss conduct?

Interpretation:

Table 1.6 and figure 1.6 shows that out of 40 respondents, 70% are of the view that the poor people are affected by police misconduct and 30% are of the view that the rich people are affected by police misconduct.

Table 4.7 police are permitted to use has much force been often necessary in making arrests

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	6	15.0
	Agree	25	62.5
	Disagree	4	10.0
	4	5	12.5
	Total	40	100.0

police are permitted to use has much force has is often necessary in making arrests

Interpretation:

Table 1.7 and Figure 1.7 shows that out 40 respondent, 15% are of the view that they are strongly agree that police are permitted to use has much force has is often necessary in making arrests, 62% are of view

that they are agree that police are permitted to use much force has is often necessary in making arrests, 10% are of the view that disagree that police are permitted to use has much force has is often necessary in making arrests and 12.5% are strongly disagree to this statement.

Table 4.8 what are some example of police miss conduct other than physical abuse

	Frequency	Percent
Valid verbal abuse	4	10.0
civil abuse	29	72.5
procedural abuse	7	17.5
Total	40	100.0

what are some exemple of police mis conduct other then physical abbuse

Interpretation:

Table 1.8 and Figure 1.8 shows that out of 40 respondents, 10% are of the view that verbal abuse is one of the example of police misconduct other than physical abuse, 72% are of view that civi abuse is police misconduct and 17% are of view that procedural abuse is police misconduct other than physical abuse.

Table 4.9 How does police miss conduct effect his community

	Frequency	Percent
Valid damage social prestige	22	55.0
financial loss	11	27.5
self-respect	7	17.5
Total	40	100.0

How does police miss conduct effect his community

Interpretation:

Table 1.9 and Figure 1.9 shows that out of 40 respondents, 55% are of the view that due to police misconduct the social prestige is damage, 27% are of the view that due to police misconduct there are financial losses and 17.5 are of view that police misconduct effects on self- respect.

Table 4.10 Do cops make he feel safe in his neighborhood

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Yes	21	52.5
	No	8	20.0
	any other	11	27.5
	Total	40	100.0

Interpretation:

Table 1.10 and Figure 1.10 shows that out of 40 respondents, 52% are of the view that they agree that they are safe in neighborhood due to police, 20% are of the view that they are not safe in neighborhood due to police.

Table 4.11 Do you feel comfortable complying with police officers

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	yes	18	45.0
	no	20	50.0
	any other	2	5.0
	Total	40	100.0

Interpretation:

Table 1.11 and Figure 1.11 shows that out of 40 respondents, 45% are of the view that they are feel comfortable complying with police officers and 50% are of the view that they are not feel comfortable complying with police officers.

H_0 = police misconduct and public trust are independent

H_1 = police misconduct and public trust are dependent

Test Statistics

	how does police mis conduct effect his community
Chi-Square	7.550 ^a
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.023

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.3.

If the p value is less than the level of significance null hypothesis is rejected and the result is statistically significant and if p value is greater than the level of significance null hypothesis is accepted and the result is statistically non-significant. In the above table p value is 0.023 which is less than the level of significance, so null hypothesis is rejected and the result is statistically significant. Here alternative hypothesis is accepted so it is concluded that police misconduct and public trust are dependent.

FINDINGS

1. Out of 40 respondents, 55% are the procedural police misconduct people often face 32% civil and 12% criminal police miss conduct people face.
2. Out of 40 respondents, 42.5% are of the view that in police misconduct includes traffic police and 32.5% narcotic police and 25% city police.
3. Out of 40 respondents, 72.5% are of the view that police misconduct is an issue in city 17.5% are of the view that police misconduct is no issue in the city.
4. Out of 40 respondents shows that 35% are of view that they feel less comfortable due to police misconduct in the neighborhood and 27.5% are of the view that they are not feeling less comfortable due to police misconduct.
5. Out of 40 respondents, 20% are of the view that there personal experience with the police and 80% are of the view there is no person with police.
6. Out of 40 respondents, 70% are of the view that the poor people are affected by police misconduct a 30% are of the view that the rich people are affected by police misconduct.
7. out of 40 respondent 1.5% are of the view that they are strongly agree that police are permitted to use has much force has is often necessary in making arrest 62% are of view that they are agree that police are permitted to use much force has is often necessary in making arrest 10% of the view that disagree that police are permitted to use has much force has is often necessary in making arrest and 12.5% are strongly disagree to statement
8. Out of 40 respondents 10% are of the view that verbal abuse is one of the police misconduct other than physical abuse 72% are of the view that civil abuse is police misconduct and 70% are of the view that procedural abuse is police misconduct other than physical abuse
9. Out of 40 respondents 55% are of the police misconduct the social prestige is damage 27% are of the view police misconduct financial losses and 17.5% are of the view police misconduct effect on self-respect
10. Out of 40 respondents 25% are of the view that they agree that they are safe in neighborhood due to police 20% are of the view

that they are not safe in neighborhood due to police.

Suggestion

Some suggestion is stated to root out the vices and improve in true relationship among the police and the people

- The inspector general of police should take some stopping to root out the corruption of the police department
- Such as police constables or officer should be suspended who take bribes for illegal treatment
- The public should be death in such a way that they may respect and trust the police
- The police department should develop the better relationship based on the justice and fair dealing with the people.

Conclusion

- To conclude the research on the socio-economic status of the complaints the nature of relationship between police misconduct and public distrust show that the maximum people do not trust police of AJK because the police trust the people in the very cruel manner in injustice of police with the people is the cause of many social problem and details dissatisfaction the research show that the police does not treat all the people in the same way as the people possessing higher status give bribe to the police and buy off dishonest police officer on the other hand the poor people cannot buy of the police by giving bribes so they are treated like animal by the police of AJK.
- All the above mention misconduct of police with the people bring about many social problem in the society has the result people do not trust the police of AJK.

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